

ISic4266

I.Sicily inscription 4266

Language

Latin

Type**Material**

stone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Seen by Orsi in June 1928 on the west slopes below the Castle

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 48 cm

Width 38 cm

Depth 43 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Augusti

Apparatus

Text of I.Lipara, after Orsi

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334856

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 85 no.1

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 48 n.235

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 748

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